

SCHOLARLY PUBLISHING: WHY SMART RESEARCHERS HESITATE TO PUBLISH IN/WITH TOP RANKING JOURNALS/PUBLISHERS

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Abstract:

Scholarly publishing is the subfield of publishing in which research work is published in the form of an academic journal article, edited book or thesis form. Due to the monopoly of top ranking publishers, the researchers are struggling to publish their research articles quickly and at low publication cost. In order to reach the research findings to entire world, every author prefers to publish in open access journal but, so called top ranking journals are charging a huge fee as article processing charges which are in general between \$1,000 to \$3,000 and some journals charges even \$5,000 apart from article submission fee. Since such journals are not paying any remuneration for peer review process, the review process and final publication take long time, generally eight to ten months. This constraint of a long time and huge cost involved in scholarly publishing made the smart publishers find an alternative strategy for publishing their research. In this paper, we have discussed why smart publishers hesitate to publish in top ranking journals and their alternative strategy based on their objectives. We have also discussed the black ocean strategy formulated by such publishers as a counter strategy to face such move.

Index Terms: Smart Researchers, Academic Publication, Scholarly Publication, Open Access Publications, Top Ranking Journals & Publishers

1. Introduction:

The two objectives of the higher education system are (i) training the students to enhance knowledge, skills, experience, and attitude and (ii) creating new knowledge by means of research. Dynamic, innovative, and experienced faculty members can achieve these objectives in higher educational institutions by means of set organizational goal, able leadership, and planned strategy. The quality of training in the higher education system can be improved by means adopting advanced, current, industry required curriculum, developing innovative pedagogy for teaching and learning processes, adding experimental learning methods in the learning process. The quality in the higher education system can be further improved by adopting choice based credit system or competency-based credit system and adopting information communication technology for adding online learning components. By providing the current information in right time through class based system and online system, students can be trained to be better decision makers by systematic analysing the problems and satiations. A substantial amount of research has been conducted in the area of quality improvement and analysis in the higher education system to provide better knowledge, skills, and experience to the students. This include Strategic Planning in Higher Education Institutions [1], Innovations and Best Practices can Transform Higher Education Institutions [2], Internal Quality Assurance Cell and its Contribution [3], Enhancement of Graduate attributes in Higher Education Institutions through Stage Models [4], Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions [5], Effective Leadership and Governance [6], Strategy Development and Deployment in Higher Education Institutions [7], Faculty Empowerment Strategies in Higher Education Institutions [8], Unique & Successful

Model in Integrated Development [9], Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education [10], Techniques for Electric Energy Auditing in Education System [11], Societal Expectation And Institutional Accountability in Higher Education [12], Methods and Approaches for Employability Skill Generation in Higher Educational Institutions [13], Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions through Best Practices in Library [14], Analysis of Academic Administrative System Implemented in Higher educational institution [15], Learning through Team Centric Exercise & Key Point Pedagogy - An effective Learning Model for Slow Learners in Higher Education Training [16], Opportunities and Challenges for Private Universities [17], Innovations in Private Universities [18], Creating Innovators through setting up organizational Vision, Mission and Core Values : a Strategic Model in Higher Education [19], Comparative Study on MBA Programmes in Private & Public Universities [20], Impact of On-line Education on Higher Education System [21], Innovations in Higher Education - A new model implemented in MCA degree programme [22], Environmental Consciousness in Higher Educational Institutions [23], Analysis of Choice Based Credit System in Higher Education [24], Innovations in Student Centric Learning – A Study of Top Business Schools [25], Innovations in Experimental Learning – A Study of World Top Business Schools [26], How to Increase Research Productivity in Higher Educational Institutions [27], Academic Support through Information System [28], Teaching - Learning Process in Higher Education Institutions [29], Maintaining Teacher Quality in Higher Education Institutions [30], Student performance and Learning Outcomes in Higher Education Institutions [31], Catering Student Enrollment and Retaining Diversity in Higher Education Institutions [32], and Student Evaluation and Reforms in Higher Education Institutions [33]. Creating new knowledge by means of research by faculty members in association with students is another major responsibility of higher education institutions irrespective of the nature and kind of higher education institution. As per recently introduced ABC model [34- 35] of measuring organizational research performance, a higher educational institution can contribute to the field of new knowledge creation by means of contributing and increasing annual research publications. As per ABC model, organizational research productivity is measured by calculating the annual research productivity index, which is based on number of research articles published in peer-reviewed journals by faculty members and students, number of books published by faculty members, number of book chapters and business cases published by faculty members and students of that organization. As per new organizational theory for the 21st century, called Theory A [36-37], by means of setting a target, motivating, continuous monitoring, and claiming accountability, faculty members and their students in higher education institution can improve their team performance to increase annual research productivity.

As a final stage of new knowledge creation, the researchers have to publish their papers in journals as referred articles, or as case studies, or as edited book chapters or as textbooks. In scholarly publishing process, the research papers have to be submitted to the journal editor as per journal format. The editor makes a subjective evaluation of the paper's quality and impact, before sending it to two or three out of a thousand possible reviewers who will make an obscure decision about the content of the paper. Sometimes this system works well, but increasingly it does not. Many review result shows that great papers have rejected for political reasons or poor ones accepted for the same. Publishing in scholarly peer-reviewed journals usually entails long delays from submission to publication. These delays slow the dissemination of scholarship and can provide a significant burden on the academic careers of authors. The shortest

overall delays occur in science technology and medical (STM) fields and the longest delay occurs in social science, arts/humanities, and business/economics. Business/economics with a delay of 18 months takes twice as long as chemistry with a 9-month average delay [38]. The publication charges of top international publishers are also shoot-up such that an author has to spend \$1000 - \$5,000 as publication charge/article processing charges to international reputed publishers. This constraint of a long time and huge cost involved in scholarly publishing made the smart publishers find an alternative strategy & to find a solution or alternative way of publishing their articles at low or zero cost and immediate reach to interested researcher community through self-online publication models. In this paper, we have discussed why smart publishers hesitate to publish in top ranking journals and their alternative strategy based on their objectives. We have also discussed the black ocean strategy formulated by such publishers as a counter strategy to face such move.

2. Objectives of Scholarly Publication:

Many experienced authors have following objectives towards publication of their research papers:

Fast Publication: An experienced author, after writing the research paper systematically and completing the internal review from his colleagues, desires to publish the paper early so that it can reach the society immediately. To support this desire, a smart author prefers monthly journals instead of quarterly or bi-annual journals because monthly journals are very active and fast in publishing work due to pressure involved for a monthly publication.

Open Access Journal: Every author expects that his/her research should reach every interested person in the world without any constraints. This is possible only in open access publication. In conventional publications with top rated publishers, the author has to sign copyright agreement to transfer the copyright of the article to the publisher. The publisher sells the article at \$30 to \$40 per copy so that the article is not allowed for free access. As a result, the article fails to attract more citations as well as fails to reach many people.

Registered Journal with ISSN: Every author prefers to publish his/her research paper in a journal which has approved ISSN number. ISSN number is allotted by the Recognised Govt. Agency of that country.

Zero or Low Processing Charges: Research scholars after writing papers on their research results by spending money, time and efforts, do not want to spend money further to publish the paper to the entire world. So if the alternative is available, they do not want to spend money further for open access publication as a fee for article processing charges. They have a question that in scholarly publication when the reviewers work is unpaid and considered as volunteered, why not publisher provide the service at voluntarily or at a very low charge.

Quick Review: Every author expects that his/her paper has to be published quickly after completion of the review process. But it is known that top level publishers usually takes 6 months to sometimes 18 months to publish papers in which the review process consumes the major part of time.

Journals Which Allows Authors to Retain Copyright of Their Work with Them: Scholarly authors prefer to keep copyright of their paper with themselves so that they can apply a patent for the work in due course and also prefer to do self-indexing. On other hand, the top level publishers try to keep copyright of the paper in their hand through a cunning copyright transfer agreement.

Journal Which has Document Identification Number (DOI) for Each Paper: The authors do not need any journal indexing except ISBN number for the journal and individual paper identification number (Document identification number-DOI) for open reference of the published paper.

Journal Impact Factor has No Significance: The journal impact factor assessed by various agencies has no significance for the researchers. The researcher can self-deposit the papers in various social research sites like Research Gate, Social Science Research Networks (SSRN), Academia.edu etc. for ubiquitous reference from everybody for free of cost. Journal impact factors are publishers gimmick for branding their journals and to increase article processing charges.

Journal Indexing has No Significance to Authors: Journal indexing has no significance to the author. The published paper indexed in google scholar is available for topic-based search and can be downloaded from any social research network site where author self-deposited the paper. As a result indexing in hundreds of indexing agencies has no importance to an individual author and it should not be a reason to increase author processing fee by publishers.

Self-depositing & Self-indexing Opportunity: Smart authors prefer to keep copyright of their articles with them and upload their papers to various free repository databases as well as social research networking sites. This encourages self-indexing and supports article citations from networked research followers.

Universal Reachability to Enhance Citation: Due to advents in Information communication technology and internet of things, present day authors are smart to upload their paper in their personal blogs, institutional websites, various free database repositories, various social research networks so that their papers are easily searchable through topic based keywords, author name, various subject classification codes etc. so that the papers reaches entire world ubiquitously. This enhances citation opportunities of their papers.

3. Objectives of Journals/Publishers:

Branding Through Journal Metric: The journal publishers follow a strategy to increase their brand by starting more number of journals in all possible areas of research. For example, Elsevier publisher has 3252 journals. They also index their journals with many indexing agencies to claim that the published paper reaches many readers.

Increasing Entry Barrier for New Journals/Publishers: The existing journal publishers try to create barriers to new entrants who wants to do journal publishing business. This is done by means of their own sponsored indexing agencies like scopus which has a policy of indexing articles of journals which have minimum ten years existence. Only journals with minimum ten years existence can become a member of indexing agencies like SCOPUS.

Enhancing Profit Through Unique Niche Creation Strategy: The journal publishers also follow a strategy to showcase themselves as members of a particular publishing group/network/ Top-ranked journals list. Such membership/ranking is used by the publishers to create Article submission fee or to increase Article Processing Charges or to increase paper download/purchase charges or to increase Annual subscription charges of their journals.

Charging More to Authors in the Name of Article Processing Charge: Many Journal publishers follow every strategy to increase the value of publishing papers in their journals in authors' point of view so that they can increase Article processing charges and Subscription charges of their journals.

Avoiding Any Expenditure for Article Review: This objective makes all journal publishers to follow a strategy to fool the reviewers by telling that review is a service and reviewer gets professional benefits instead of financial benefits.

Keeping Copyright of Articles in Publishers' Hand: This objective of transferring copyright of the papers from authors to publishers provides an opportunity to the publishers to sell the papers a considerably high price for long-time. The publisher can make a good amount of profit by selling authors papers once they are published in their journals. Publishers are always trying to enlarge Green Open access embargo time as long as possible usually from one year to three years.

Selling Printed Journals to Worldwide Libraries to Earn a Maximum Profit: All publishers recover their expenditure by supplying printed journals to individuals and libraries worldwide. By creating brand name for their journals and by means of various kind of black ocean strategy, publishers try to get orders for subscription of their journals by many public sector universities and institutions even if some times the articles are freely downloadable from journal website as open access articles.

Use of Black Ocean Strategy to Create False Journal Rating to Attract More Authors: Another objective of many publishers is to get false popularity by illegally raising journal rating and journal impact factors.

Increasing the Review Time, Publication Time to Show that their Journals are Highly Demanded: Most of the journals have an objective to raise their demand through their strategy of increasing review time, publication time after paper acceptance.

Objective to Show their Journals Demand by Increased Article Rejection Ratio: Both reputed and new publishers show that their journals are in high demand by showing false article rejection ratio. By showing increased articles rejection ratio, publishers thinks that they can raise article processing charge or decrease the bargaining power of authors for waiver of article processing charges.

4. Strategies of Top Publishers:

In the scholarly publishing business, many of the top publishers who publish hundreds to thousands of journals use various strategies to enhance their profit by decreasing the bargaining power of authors. Many top level publishers introduced fees for submitting the articles for the review and publication. Even though they are not paying any review fee to the reviewers, they have developed the habit of collecting paper submission fee of several hundred dollars. For open access articles, the top publisher's charges from \$500 to \$5,000 as article processing fee and by mixing open access articles with other paid downloadable articles, publishers charges the considerable amount of Journal annual subscription fees from the libraries. Wherever, the publisher fails to collect open access article processing charges from the author, through a stringent copyright transfer certificate, publisher charges maximum fee (\$30 to \$50 per article) as individual article downloadable charge for considerably long time to enhance their profit. Table 1 contains some of the world top publishers with the number of journals they publish along with the open access article processing charges to be collected from the authors and individual article downloading charges. While analysing the data given in table 1 from author's point of view, even though he is the center of publication business, the entire business model has neglected the importance of the authors of the research papers and hence made the business model as negative sum game.

Table 1: List of some of top publishers with the number of journals, APC, and Article download charge.

S.No	Journal Publisher	No. of Journals (>=)	Indexing	Author Publication Charge (APC)	Article download Charge
1	Elsevier Journals	3,252	Scopus ScienceDirect	\$ 500 - \$5,000 Average \$ 3,000	\$ 35.95 to \$ 50
2	Springer-Verlag	2,700	Google/Scopus	\$3,000	\$ 30 to \$ 40
3	John Wiley and Sons	2,380	Scopus	\$ 800 to \$4,500	\$ 38
4	Taylor and Francis	2,100	Google/Scopus	\$ 2,950	\$50
5	Sage Publications	1,300	Scopus	\$695 to \$ 3,000	\$ 36
6	SciELO	1,249	Google/Scopus	R\$1000,00	Open Access
7	Walter de Gruyter	913	Google/Scopus	P 1,000 to P 1,500	\$227/Issue
8	RMIT Publishing	415			
9	Inderscience Publishers	391	Google/Scopus	P 2,000	\$40
10	Hindawi Publishing Corporation	366	Google/Scopus	\$ 600 to \$2,000	Open Access
11	Cambridge University Press	329	Google/CrossRef and Scopus	\$1,500 - \$3,000	Open Access & Paid Access \$37.50
12	Oxford University Press (OUP)	310	Google/CrossRef and Scopus	\$1,700- \$ 3,000	Open Access & Paid Access \$ 40
13	Emerald	308	Google/CrossRef and Scopus	P 996 to P 1,650	Open Access & Paid Access \$ 32
18	Biomed Central Ltd.	268	Google/Scopus	\$ 2,145	Open Access
20	Scientific Research Publishing	214	Google/Crossref	\$300 to \$1,200	Open Access
22	Medknow Publishers	378	Google/Scopus	Free	Open Access & \$20 to \$100/Article
23	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)	174	Google/Crossref	\$110 to \$200 per page	\$33/Article
24	Thieme Publishing Group	157	Google/Scopus	\$ 1,500	Open Access & Paid Access \$ 32/Article
25	SpringerOpen	160	Google/Scopus	\$ 980 - \$3000	Open Access
26	Brill Academic Publishers	200	Google/Scopus	\$1,830 to \$ 2,745	Open Access & Paid Access \$ 30/Article
27	IGI Global	180	Google/Scopus	\$ 1,500	Open Access & Paid Access \$ 30/Article
28	Science and Education Publishing	72	Google/Crossref	\$ 150 - \$360	Open Access
29	World Scientific, Singapore	120	Google/Scopus	\$ 1,500	Open Access & Paid Access \$ 30/Article
30	Academic Journals	73	Cross Ref DOI	\$ 550 - \$ 750	Open Access
31	Science Publishing Group	110	Cross Ref DOI	\$ 370 to \$ 90	Open Access

In subscription model of journal publication, the publication cost is recovered by collecting subscription charge by libraries and other readers. This subscription fee may be an annual subscription fee or one-time individual paper downloading fees. An alternative to the subscription model of journal publishing is the open access journal model, which typically involves a publication charge being paid by the author. Top journals typically charge several thousand dollars as open access processing charge. The online distribution of individual articles and academic journals then takes place without charge to readers. Most open access journals remove all the financial, technical, and legal barriers that limit access to academic materials to paying customers. The tables 2 to table 8 contain detailed information on author publication fee and paper download charge of ten journals of some reputed/top publishers.

Table 2: Ten Elsevier Journals financial information

S.No	Elsevier Journals	Author Publication Fee/Institutional Subscription fee	Paper download Charge
1	International Journal of Pharmaceutics (12 Issues)	OAF \$3,500 \$ 12,320/Year	\$41.95
2	International Journal of Human-Computer Studies (12 Issues)	OAF \$ 3,100 \$3,579/Year	\$36
3	International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer(12 Issues)	OAF \$3,300 \$10,050	\$40
4	The International Journal of Mechanical Sciences (IJMS) (15 Issues)	OAF \$3,300 \$5,024/year	\$36
5	International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems (JEPE) (10 Issues)	OAF \$3,300 \$3,434	\$40
6	International Journal of Obstetric Anaesthesia (4 Issues)	OAF \$ 2,500 \$802/Year	\$31.50
7	International Journal of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery (12 Issues)	OAF \$3300 \$ 1,313	\$31.50
8	International Journal of Surgery (IJS) (12 Issues)	OAF \$ 2,500 \$500	\$31.50
9	International Journal of Biological Macromolecules (12 issues)	OAF \$3,000 \$3,550	\$ 36
10	Infrared Physics & Technology (6 Issues)	OAF \$2,200 \$2,539	\$36

Table 3: Ten Springer-Verlag Journals financial information

S.No	Springer-VerlagJournals	Author Publication Fee	Paper Download Charge
1	Journal of Big Data (12 Issues)	OAF \$1,155	Free
2	International Journal of Concrete Structures and Materials (4 Issues)	OAF \$1,230	Free
3	Journal of Solid State Lighting (4 Issues)	OAF \$1,230	Free
4	Pharmaceutical Medicine (6 Issues)	OAF \$3,000	Free
5	American Journal of Clinical Dermatology (6 Issues)	OAF \$3,000	Free
6	International Journal of Computer Vision(15 Issues)	OAF \$3,000 P 15,150	\$ 40/paper
7	Journal of Medical Systems (12 Issues)	OAF \$3,000 P 15,150	\$ 40/paper
8	Swarm Intelligence (4 Issues)	OAF \$3,000 P 15,150	\$ 40/paper
9	Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Medicine (12 Issues)	OAF \$3,000 P 15,150	\$40/paper
10	International Journal of Mechanics and Materials in Design (4 Issues)	OAF \$3,000 P 7,625	\$40/paper

Table 4: Ten Taylor and Francis Journals financial information

S.No	Taylor and Francis Journals	Author Publication Fee &	Annual Subscription fee	Paper download Charge
1	Journal of Sustainable Tourism (12 Issues)	OAF \$2950	\$1,814	\$41
2	Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Education (4 Issues)	OAF \$2950	\$208	\$41
3	Journal of Sport Psychology in Action (3 Issues)	OAF \$2950	\$261	\$41
4	Information Systems Management (4 Issues)	OAF \$2950	\$330	\$50
5	Applied Artificial Intelligence (10 Issues)	OAF \$2950	\$2087	\$50
6	The Journal of Forensic Psychiatry & Psychology (6 Issues)	OAF \$2950	\$1,336	\$41
7	Journal of Essential Oil Research (6 Issues)	OAF \$2950	\$1,271	\$50
8	Marine Biology Research (10 Issues)	OAF \$2950	\$882	\$50
9	Applied Neuropsychology: Adult (6 Issues)	OAF \$2950	\$1,513	\$41
10	Journal of Trauma & Dissociation (5 Issues)	OAF \$2950	\$665	\$41

Table 5: Ten John Wiley and Sons Journals Financial Information

S.No	John Wiley and Sons Journals	Open Access Publication Fee	Paper Download Charge	Annual Subscription Charges
1	Strategic Management Journal (13 Issues)	\$ 3000	Free	\$ 3,172
2	Contemporary Accounting Research (4 Issues)	\$ 3000	Free	\$ 822
3	Human Resource Management (6 Issues)	Free	\$ 38	\$ 383
4	Journal of Accounting Research (5 Issues)	\$ 500 (submission fee)	\$ 38	\$1,561
5	Journal of Medical Radiation Sciences(4 Issues)	\$ 1560	Free	Online only
6	The Journal of Pathology: Clinical Research (4 Issues)	\$ 2,000	Free	Online only
7	Plant Biotechnology Journal (9 Issues)	\$ 2,720	Free	Online only
8	Thoracic Cancer (6 Issues)	\$ 2,000	Free	Online only
9	Journal of Management Studies (8 Issues)	\$ 3,000	\$38	\$ 3,123
10	Production and Operations Management (6 Issues)	\$ 3,000	\$38	\$696

Table 6: Ten Sage Publications Journals financial information

S.No	Sage Publications Journals	Author Publication Fee	Annual Subscription	Paper Download Charge
1	Journal of Hand Surgery (12 Issues)	No OAF	\$1,579/Year	\$40
2	Clinical EEG and Neuroscience (4 Issues)	No OAF	\$306/Year	\$ 40
3	Journal of International Medical Research (6 Issues)	\$450 per page	Online only	Free Download
4	International Journal of Surgical Pathology (8 Issues)	No OAF	\$1,230	\$40
5	Journal of Cerebral Blood Flow & Metabolism (12 Issues)	1,600 Euro for OAF	\$1,573	\$40
6	Textile Research Journal (18 Issues)	No OAF	\$2,758	\$ 40
7	Journal of Business and Technical Communication (4 Issues)	No OAF	\$789	\$36
8	Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures (18 Issues)	No OAF	\$4,098	\$40
9	Indian Journal of Corporate Governance (2 Issues)	No OAF	\$315	\$36
10	International Journal of Cross Cultural Management(3 Issues)	No OAF	\$757	\$ 36

Table 7: Ten Inderscience Publications Journals financial information

S.No	Inderscience Publishers Journals	Author Publication Fee	Annual Subscription	Paper Download Charge
1	International Journal of Ad Hoc and Ubiquitous Computing, (12 Issues)	P 2,000	\$1.415	\$40
2	International Journal of Applied Decision Sciences (4 Issues)	P 2,000	\$685	\$40
3	International Journal of Innovation in Education (4 Issues)	P 2,000	\$685	\$40
4	International Journal of Big Data Intelligence (4 Issues)	P 2,000	\$685	\$40
5	International Journal of Applied Cryptography (4 Issues)	P 2,000	\$685	\$40
6	International Journal of Mobile Learning and Organisation (4 Issues)	P 2,000	\$685	\$ 40
7	International Journal of Biotechnology (4 Issues)	P 2,000	\$685	\$ 40
8	African Journal of Economic and Sustainable Development (4 Issues)	P 2,000	\$685	\$ 40
9	International Journal of Electric and Hybrid Vehicles (4 Issues)	P 2,000	\$685	\$ 40
10	International Journal of Learning Technology (4 Issues)	P 2,000	\$685	\$ 40

Table 8: Ten Hindawi Publishing Corporation Journals financial information

S.No	Hindawi Publishing Corporation Journals	Author Publication Fee	Annual Subscription	Paper Download Charge
1	International Journal of Antennas and Propagation (12 Issues)	OAF \$1,750	\$895	Open Access
2	International Journal of Chemical Engineering (9 Issues)	OAF \$1250	\$395	Open Access
3	International Journal of Photoenergy (9 Issues)	OAF \$ 1,500	\$795	Open Access
4	International Journal of Optics (9 Issues)	OAF \$ 1,000	\$295	Open Access
5	Journal of Computer Networks and Communications	OAF \$ 1,000	\$595	Open Access
6	Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing	OAF \$2,000	\$395	Open Access
7	Journal of Engineering	OAF \$1,250	\$295	Open Access
8	Advances in Neuroscience	OAF \$ 600	\$195	Open Access
9	Case Reports in Medicine	OAF \$ 400	\$ 195	Open Access
10	BioMed Research International	OAF \$2,000	\$295	Open Access

Open access has been criticized on cost and quality grounds, as the desire of publishers to maximize publishing fees could cause some journals to relax the standard of peer review. It may be criticized on financial grounds as well because the necessary publication fees have proven to be higher than originally expected. But the argument of open access advocates is that because open access is as much based on peer reviewing as traditional publishing, the quality should be the same. It has also been argued that good research done by the researchers who cannot afford to pay for open access might not get published at all, but most open access journals permit the waiver of the fee for financial hardship or authors in underdeveloped countries. In any case, for smart authors have the option of self-archiving their articles in their institutional repositories or any public social research network sites in order to make them open access, whether or not they publish them in a journal.

5. Strategies of Top Management Journals:

Table 9 contains list of financial times magazines' top 45 Business management and Economics Journals with their Open Access Author Charges, Article download charges, and Annual subscription charges. Table 10 shows the processing time of submitted articles in some of the top-level journals. While studying the cost of publishing or allowing top journals to do huge profit, smart authors likely to find alternative and free publication opportunities using changes in publication models online without losing author publication citation index. This is due to opportunities available to present day authors to self-publishing online without any cost for self-archiving & indexing sites for Scholar Publishing by Authors. Table 11 contains a list of Self-Archiving & indexing Sites for Scholar Publishing by Authors.

This is also due to the fact that by seeing such trend of self-publication by many smart authors, publishers are now doing a self-evaluation to correct their mistakes including decreasing publication fee or 50 to 100% fee waiver for developing country authors, decreasing article processing time etc.

Table 9: List if Financial Times top 45 Journals

S.No	Journal	Submission Charge/ Open Access Charge	Article Download Charge	Annual Subscription Charge
1	Academy of Management Journal	-	\$25	\$220
2	Academy of Management Perspectives (Quarterly)	No	\$ 25	\$ 170
3	Academy of Management Review	No	\$ 25	\$220
4	Accounting, Organisations and Society (Elsevier)	Free Submission \$ 1800	\$ 40	\$ 3,172
5	The Accounting Review (American Accounting Association)	\$ 400 Submission	\$ 25	No Print
6	Administrative Science Quarterly (Cornell University)	Free submission \$ 395	\$ 36	\$ 310
7	American Economic Review (American Economic Association) (12 Issues)	\$200	\$9.50	\$595
8	California Management Review (UC Berkeley)	Free submission No open Access	\$39/issue	\$ 109
9	Contemporary Accounting Research (Wiley)	Free submission \$3.000	\$ 38	\$ 822
10	Econometrica (Econometric Society, Wiley)	Free submission No open Access	\$ 38	\$ 660
11	Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice (Baylor University, Wiley)	Free submission \$3.000	\$ 38	\$ 942
12	Harvard Business Review (Harvard Business School Publishing)	-	-	\$ 16.95/Issue
13	Human Resource Management (Wiley)	Free submission No open Access	\$ 38	\$ 1,368
14	Information Systems Research (Informs)	Free submission \$ 3,000	\$ 30	\$ 585
15	Journal of Accounting and Economics (Elsevier) (6 Issues)	\$ 1,800	\$40	\$2,296
16	Journal of Accounting Research (University of Chicago, Wiley)	\$500 submission fee	\$ 38	\$1,561
17	Journal of Applied Psychology (American Psychological Association)	Free submission No open Access	\$ 12	\$ 1,441
18	Journal of Business Ethics (Kluwer Academic)	Free \$ 3000	\$ 40	12,521Euro
19	Journal of Business Venturing (Elsevier) (6 Issues)	\$1,800	\$36	\$1,754

20	Journal of Consumer Psychology (Elsevier) (4 Issues)	\$1,800	\$36	\$1,041
21	Journal of Consumer Research (University of Chicago)	Free	\$39	\$603
22	Journal of Finance (Wiley) (6 Issues)	Submission Fee \$150	\$38	\$704
23	Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis (Cambridge University Press)	Submission fee \$350	\$37.50	\$628
24	Journal of Financial Economics (Elsevier) (12 Issues)	\$1,800	\$40	\$4,276
25	Journal of International Business Studies (Academy of International Business)	Free \$2,600	\$40	\$629
26	Journal of Management Studies (Wiley)	Free \$3,000	\$38	\$3,123
27	Journal of Marketing (American Marketing Association)	Free -	\$30	\$435
28	Journal of Marketing Research (American Marketing Association)	Free -	\$30	\$435
29	Journal of Operations Management (Elsevier)	Free \$2,000	\$42	\$1,096
30	Journal of Political Economy (University of Chicago)	\$125 submission fee \$2,500	\$10	\$535
31	Journal of the American Statistical Association (American Statistical Association)	Free \$2,950	\$46	\$928 4 Issues
32	Management Science (Informs)	Free \$3,000	\$30	\$1235 12 Issues
33	Marketing Science (Informs)	Free \$3,000	\$30	\$618 6 Issues
34	MIS Quarterly (Management Information Systems Research Centre, University of Minnesota)	Free	\$10	\$475/Year 4 Issues
35	Operations Research (Informs)	Free \$3,000	\$30	\$736 6 Issues
36	Organization Science (Informs)	Free \$3,000	\$30	\$629 6 Issues
37	Organization Studies (SAGE) (12 Issues)	Free \$3,000	\$36	P 1,347 12 Issues
38	Organizational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes (Academic Press)	Free \$1,800	\$36	\$2715 6 Issues
39	Production and Operations Management (Wiley)	Free \$3,000	\$38	\$696 12 Issues
40	Quarterly Journal of Economics (MIT)	Free -	\$40	\$679 4 Issues
41	Rand Journal of Economics (The Rand Corporation, Wiley)	Free \$3,000	\$38/Article	\$527 4 Issues
42	Review of Accounting Studies (Springer)	Free \$3,000	\$40/Article	7499 Euros 4 Issues
43	Review of Financial Studies (Oxford University Press)	Free -	\$40/Article	\$716 12 Issues
44	Sloan Management Review (MIT)	-	Free	\$75 12 Issues
45	Strategic Management Journal (Wiley)	Free \$3,000	\$38/Article	\$3172 12 Issues

Table 10: Processing Time of Submitted Articles in Top Level Journals

S.No	Journals/Publishers	Processing Time For Publication	Green Open Access Embargo Time
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1	Elsevier Journals	3 – 12 months	24 months
2	Springer-Verlag Journals	3 – 12 months	24 months
3	Taylor and Francis Journals	3 – 12 months	24 months
4	John Wiley and Sons Journals	3 – 9 months	24 months
5	Emerald	3-8 months	24 months
6	IGI Global	2 - 6 months	Immediate
7	World Scientific, Singapore	2 – 6 months	12 months

Table 11: List of Self-Archiving & indexing Sites for Scholar Publishing by Authors

S.No	Self-Archiving & Social Networking Sites	Website of Service Provider	Nature of Acceptance
1	ResearchGate	www.researchgate.net	Direct deposit
2	Social Science Research Network	http://www.ssrn.com/	Based on Review
3	Academia.edu	www.academia.edu	Direct deposit
4	MPRA Munich Personal RePEc Archive	https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/cgi 37,274 records	Based on Review
5	<u>Mendeley</u>	https://www.mendeley.com	Direct deposit
6	Selected works	https://works.bepress.com/	Direct deposit
7	OpenAIR	https://www.openaire.eu/ 10843636 Articles	Direct deposit
8	ORCID	http://orcid.org/	Direct deposit
9	PubMed	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed 26 million citations	-
10	Organizational Research website	-	-
11	Individual research blog	-	-
12	Google scholar (for listing, hyper linking & Citation)	https://scholar.google.co.in/	Through hyper linking
13	Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/deposit/	Direct deposit & DOI

By foreseeing such move of smart authors, top journals are trying to keep the authors in their business model by making following improvements in their classical styles:

- ✓ Starting more journals in different subjects to provide specialized journals in each area of subjects.
- ✓ Simplifying the submission process.
- ✓ Decreasing the waiting time from submission to publication.
- ✓ Speeding up review process by offering non-financial incentives like one-year free journal subscription to reviewers, discount for reviewers paper publications, etc.
- ✓ Gold and green open access options with reduced embargo time for self-archiving.
- ✓ Document Identification number through Cross reference for published article unique identification.

6. Peer Review: Why it is Losing Importance:

Peer review is a central concept for most academic publishing; other scholars in a field must find a work sufficiently high in quality for it to merit publication. A secondary benefit of the process is an indirect guard against plagiarism since reviewers are usually familiar with the sources consulted by the author(s). Peer review process is losing its importance due to the reason that many experts in the field are not ready to waste their time for reviewing others papers but spend their valuable time for their own research. As a result, publishers are appointing non-expert people as full-time reviewers. Such review process is not effective and does not make any difference in quality. Peer review is criticized based on following questions: How two reviewers

make difference? How to modify the submitted paper based on non-acceptable suggestions? Perhaps the most widely recognized failing of peer review is its inability to ensure the identification of high-quality work. The availability of free Automatic Plagiarism Checkers simplified the work of authors and they can pre-check their paper for plagiarism. The authors can also use readymade automatic grammar checking software which is also available free of cost. These improve the quality of paper so that the peer review process is losing its importance and also the author can invite comments on his paper by self-publishing the paper in social research networks. This process allows the author to improve the quality of the paper before publishing it in a journal. Alternatives the author also improve the quality of the paper by means of following way before sending it to peer reviewed journals :

- ✓ Conference Presentation
- ✓ Conference Review for Proceedings
- ✓ Publication in online media for comments
- ✓ Focus/Peer group discussion by author

7. Smart Author's Strategies:

Based on the objectives of scholarly publication of Authors, they should have following smart strategies to avoid spending money for journal publication. Some of the smart author's strategies are listed in table 12.

- ✓ Request the paper review from institutional colleagues
- ✓ Check the grammar mistakes using free English grammar checking software
- ✓ Check the plagiarism level using free plagiarism checker and improve and give additional references if required.
- ✓ Upload the paper as working paper in author's self-blog, institutional website, and various social research network site and invite comments for improvement.
- ✓ Choose journals which have zero or low and affordable article processing charge with valid ISSN number and open access model to every reader.
- ✓ Check the copyright transfer document and ensure that the copyright is with the author.
- ✓ Deposit the published paper in all available research paper repositories and social research networks for maximum visibility.
- ✓ Cite your own publications in your future publications if they are in the relevant field.
- ✓ Find unique DOI number for your papers published in journals/self-publication from various free DOI service providers like zenodo [39].

Table 12: Smart author Strategy

S.No	Strategy	Strategy Type
1	Self publishing	Low/zero cost strategy
2	Self indexing	Maximum reachable
3	Self citation	Survival strategy
4	Digital publication & Circulation	Sustainable strategy
5	Listing & Highlighting publications in all possible social media	Growth strategy
6	DOI numbering	Unique paper identification Strategy

8. Publishers Black Ocean Strategy as Counter Strategy:

Top publishers are developing various competitive strategies to face competition among rivals and to block new entrants to journal publication business. They are searching monopoly strategies to keep them in the blue ocean by creating their own niche and safety zone.

By creating gold access which is open access to published article and the author gets the freedom to host the paper in any other open network, they are also trying to follow sustainable called green ocean strategy. By means of playing following survival strategies called black ocean strategy, they are trying to face and survive in the scholarly publishing business.

- ✓ Influencing in the process of journal ranking published by national and international magazines.
- ✓ Lobbying in Education Departments of the countries to formulate favourable policies and additional weight age to research publications in so-called top journals.
- ✓ Bribing university officials and administrators of research organizations to formulate promotion policies of the faculty members and researchers in favour of them.
- ✓ In the name of journal indexing, they are trying to formulate their own niche like Web of science indexing, Scopus indexing etc.
- ✓ Controlling the authors through copyright clauses.
- ✓ New models of open access called Gold and Green Access.
- ✓ Creating a journal metric called Journal Impact Factor and highlighting it in the homepage of the journals.

9. Conclusion:

In order to reach the research findings to entire world, every author prefers to publish in open access journal but, so called top ranking journals are charging a huge fee as article processing charges which are in general between \$1,000 to \$3,000 and some journals charges even \$5,000 apart from article submission fee. Since such journals are not paying any remuneration for peer review process, the review process and final publication takes long time, generally eight to ten months. This constraint of a long-time and huge cost involved in scholarly publishing made the smart publishers find an alternative strategy for publishing their research. In this paper, we have discussed why smart publishers hesitate to publish in top ranking journals and their alternative strategy based on their objectives. We have also discussed the black ocean strategy formulated by such publishers as a counter strategy to face such move.

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